

DIGITIZATION AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract

The article discusses trends in the spread of digitalization and its use by enterprises in the Kyrgyz Republic. The purpose of the study is to determine the level of digitalization of enterprises and consider further prospects for digitalization and the use of Artificial intelligence in managing an organization and promoting a product. The authors analyzed the dynamics of the number of small and medium-sized enterprises, number of enterprises and organizations, using ICT, Availability of own Web-site in the Kyrgyz Republic for 2018-2022, factors contributing to the spread of digitalization in the Kyrgyz Republic are identified, prospects for using Artificial intelligence in managing an organization and promoting a product are considered.

Keywords: digitalization, Artificial intelligence, small and medium-sized enterprises, personal computers, Web site, E-commerce

Introduction

Digitization is transforming the business landscape, offering organizations new ways to operate, compete, and grow. This process involves converting analog information into digital formats, leading to increased efficiency, enhanced data management, and the potential for innovative business models.

Digitization refers to the process of converting physical or analog information into digital form. This transition encompasses a wide range of activities, including:

- replacing paper documents with digital files, enabling easier storage, retrieval, and sharing;
- implementing software solutions to automate repetitive and manual tasks, increasing efficiency;
- leveraging digital data to gain insights, make informed decisions, and predict future trends;
- incorporating technologies such as cloud computing, the internet of things (IoT), and artificial intelligence (AI) into business operations.

Digitization offers numerous benefits that significantly contribute to the development and competitiveness of organizations. Enhanced efficiency is one of the primary advantages, as automated processes streamline operations, reducing the time and effort needed to com-

plete tasks and leading to faster turnaround times. Additionally, digital systems minimize human errors associated with manual data entry and processing, resulting in more accurate outcomes.

Improved data management is another key benefit. Digital documents are easily accessible, searchable, and retrievable, which boosts overall productivity. Moreover, advanced security measures protect digital data through encryption, reducing the risk of data breaches and enhancing overall security [1,2,3].

Cost savings are also a major advantage of digitization. By reducing reliance on paper, physical storage, and manual labor, organizations can achieve significant cost reductions. Automation further contributes to cost savings by freeing up human resources to focus on more strategic and value-added activities.

Digitization fosters innovation and agility, enabling organizations to quickly adapt to market changes and customer demands. It also opens up opportunities for new business models, such as e-commerce and digital services, facilitating growth and expansion [4,5,6,7].

However, digitization presents several challenges that organizations must address to ensure successful implementation. Technical challenges include the complexity and cost of integrating new digital technologies

with existing legacy systems and the careful planning required for data migration from analog to digital formats.

Cultural resistance is another challenge, as employees may be hesitant to adapt to new processes and workflows. Effective change management strategies and training programs are essential to address these issues and bridge the skills gap associated with the transition to digital operations.

Finally, security and privacy concerns must be managed carefully. Increased reliance on digital systems exposes organizations to cybersecurity risks, making it necessary to implement robust security measures. Ensuring compliance with data privacy regulations and protecting sensitive information are critical to maintaining trust and safeguarding data.

Results

Small businesses and medium-sized enterprises form the backbone of the Kyrgyz economy, providing employment opportunities and contributing to the country's GDP. This report will look at the annual changes in the number of these enterprises and analyze the potential factors influencing these dynamics.

The dynamics of the number of small and medium-sized enterprises in the Kyrgyz Republic from 2018 to 2022 reflect a mixture of growth, resilience, and challenges. While the number of small businesses showed steady growth overall, medium-sized enterprises experienced more fluctuation, particularly impacted by the pandemic (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Dynamics of the number of small and medium-sized enterprises in the Kyrgyz Republic for 2018-2022, units

Source: compiled according to data from the National Statistics Committee of the Kyrgyz Republic [8]

The adoption of ICT by enterprises is a positive trend, showing increasing digitalization, which is crucial for competitiveness and efficiency in the modern business environment.

Overall, the trends indicate a resilient SME sector that is gradually adapting to new economic realities and embracing digital transformation. Continued support and conducive policies will be essential to sustain and enhance this growth trajectory.

The adoption and utilization of personal computers (PCs) are critical indicators of technological advancement and digital integration in any country. In the Kyrgyz Republic, the number of personal computers has been steadily increasing over the years, reflecting

the growing importance of digital tools in various sectors. This report examines the dynamics of the number of personal computers in the Kyrgyz Republic from 2018 to 2022, highlighting trends, factors influencing growth, and the impact on the country's digital landscape.

The total number of personal computers in the Kyrgyz Republic has shown a consistent upward trend from 2018 to 2022. This growth can be attributed to several factors, including increased demand for digital services, greater accessibility to technology, and the necessity of remote work and education during the COVID-19 pandemic (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Dynamics of the number of personal computers in the Kyrgyz Republic for 2018-2022, units
 Source: compiled according to data from the National Statistics Committee of the Kyrgyz Republic [8]

Several factors contributed to the spread of digitalization in the Kyrgyz Republic:

- as the economy grows, disposable incomes increase, allowing more individuals and businesses to invest in personal computers.
- policies aimed at promoting digital literacy and access to technology have supported the proliferation of pcs.
- the covid-19 pandemic underscored the necessity of digital tools, significantly boosting pc adoption for remote work, education, and healthcare.
- advances in technology have made pcs more affordable and accessible, driving higher adoption rates.
- the increasing number of personal computers has had a profound impact on the Kyrgyz Republic's digital landscape:
 - enhanced access to digital tools has facilitated remote learning, bridging educational gaps and expanding opportunities.
 - businesses have become more efficient and competitive by leveraging digital technologies for operations, marketing, and customer engagement.
 - telehealth services have expanded, providing greater access to healthcare, especially in remote areas.
 - e-governance initiatives have improved the delivery of public services, making them more accessible and efficient.

The proliferation of the internet and digital technologies has made having a web presence an essential aspect for businesses, organizations, and individuals alike. A website serves as a digital storefront, providing information, services, and engagement opportunities for a global audience.

Own websites play an important role for businesses, having a significant impact on various aspects

of their activities. They provide a company's online presence and visibility. A website is the face of a company on the Internet, representing the brand and ensuring its recognition. This is an important tool for creating an image and increasing customer confidence. A well-optimized website helps improve a company's visibility in search engines, attracting more potential customers.

Marketing and promotion also benefit from having a website. It allows companies to precisely target marketing efforts by providing information, promotions and content relevant to different audience segments. Through blogs, articles and videos, companies can attract and retain customers by providing them with valuable information and advice.

Sales and e-commerce benefit greatly from websites. They provide a platform to sell products and services directly to customers, expanding geographic boundaries and increasing revenue. Using analytics tools, companies can track visitor behavior, optimize pages to increase conversions, and improve user experience.

Customer support and communication also become more efficient through websites. Frequently asked questions and support sections help customers find answers to their questions on their own, reducing the burden on support teams. The ability to easily contact a company through feedback forms or contact details leads to better customer interaction and increased customer satisfaction.

The availability of own websites in the Kyrgyz Republic from 2018 to 2022 shows a positive trend overall, with significant growth in recent years. This trend reflects the increasing importance of digital presence in modern society. The fluctuations observed during this period underscore the impact of external factors such as economic conditions and the COVID-19 pandemic on digital adoption (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Availability of own Web-site in the Kyrgyz Republic for 2018-2022, units

Source: compiled according to data from the National Statistics Committee of the Kyrgyz Republic [8]

Websites provide detailed information about products and services. They include detailed descriptions and specifications to help customers make informed decisions. Posting reviews and ratings allows customers to share their experiences and opinions, which can have a positive impact on the company's reputation.

Customer loyalty and building a community around the brand are also supported through websites. These may include loyalty programs that encourage repeat purchases and customer retention. Integration with social media platforms helps create communities around the brand and actively interact with the audience [9,10].

Websites encourage innovation and feedback. They can serve as a platform for testing new products and collecting customer feedback through surveys and questionnaires. Regular updates and news publications on the website allow customers to keep abreast of the latest events and innovations of the company.

Thus, business websites are a powerful tool that helps companies attract customers, improve their experience, increase sales and remain competitive in the market.

Businesses with websites can reach a wider audience, expanding their market beyond geographical limitations. Websites provide platforms for customer interaction, feedback, and personalized services, improving customer satisfaction and loyalty.

The rise of online stores has boosted the e-commerce sector, providing consumers with more options and convenience.

Educational institutions and platforms with websites offer remote learning opportunities, making education more accessible. Websites serve as important sources of information, providing timely updates, resources, and services to the public.

Government websites enhance the delivery of public services, making them more efficient and accessible to citizens. Websites improve transparency and accountability by providing public access to information and services.

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As the digital landscape continues to evolve, further investment in digital infrastructure, along with supportive policies and programs, will be crucial for sustaining and enhancing the growth of online presence in the Kyrgyz Republic. This will ensure that businesses, individuals, and public institutions can fully leverage the benefits of the digital age, contributing to the country's overall development and global integration.

Conclusion

Digitization is a powerful catalyst for the development and growth of organizations. By enhancing efficiency, improving data management, reducing costs, and fostering innovation, digitization enables businesses to remain competitive in an increasingly digital world. However, organizations must navigate technical, cultural, and security challenges to fully realize the benefits of digitization. With strategic planning, effective change management, and a focus on continuous improvement, organizations can successfully leverage digitization to achieve sustainable growth and long-term success.

The dynamics of the number of personal computers in the Kyrgyz Republic from 2018 to 2022 illustrate a clear trend towards increased digital adoption. Despite challenges such as economic fluctuations and the COVID-19 pandemic, the country has made significant strides in integrating digital technologies into everyday life. This growth reflects the broader global trend towards digital transformation and highlights the critical role of personal computers in shaping the future of the Kyrgyz Republic's economy and society. Continued investment in technology and supportive policies will be essential to sustaining this momentum and ensuring that the benefits of digitization are widely shared.

E-commerce is becoming an important tool for entrepreneurship thanks to digitalization, which includes the creation of online shopping and payment platforms, and the use of artificial intelligence, which supports recommendation systems, analysis of consumer behav-

ior and dynamic pricing. E-commerce is becoming increasingly important due to digitalization, which includes the creation of online shopping and payment platforms, as well as the use of artificial intelligence, which supports recommendation systems, analysis of consumer behavior and dynamic pricing.

Artificial intelligence is rapidly becoming part of the activities of managers and is widely used in managing an organization and promoting a product. It plays a transformative role in business across various sectors, enabling efficiency, innovation, and improved decision-making. One of the key areas where AI impacts business is automation and efficiency. For example, Robotic Process Automation (RPA) automates routine tasks such as data entry, payroll processing, and inventory management, freeing up human resources for more strategic tasks. Similarly, AI algorithms predict demand, manage inventory, and optimize logistics in supply chain operations, reducing costs and improving delivery times.

Another significant area is data analysis and decision-making. Predictive analytics analyzes historical data to forecast future trends, customer behaviors, and market conditions, aiding in strategic planning. Additionally, AI-driven business intelligence tools provide real-time insights and data visualization, supporting data-driven decision-making.

AI also greatly enhances customer experience. Chatbots and virtual assistants provide 24/7 customer support, handle inquiries, and resolve issues quickly, improving customer satisfaction. Furthermore, AI algorithms analyze customer data to deliver personalized recommendations, offers, and content, enhancing the overall customer experience.

In terms of product and service innovation, AI aids in designing and testing new products through simulations and rapid prototyping. AI-driven solutions like predictive maintenance in manufacturing and smart scheduling in services improve product reliability and customer satisfaction.

Marketing and sales benefit from AI through targeted marketing, where AI analyzes customer data to identify target audiences, optimize marketing campaigns, and increase conversion rates. AI also predicts sales trends, identifies high-value leads, and recommends pricing strategies to boost sales performance.

Human resources departments leverage AI for talent acquisition by streamlining the recruitment process, screening resumes, matching candidates, and predicting job fit. AI also analyzes employee feedback and performance data to improve workplace satisfaction and productivity.

In risk management and fraud detection, AI systems detect unusual patterns and anomalies in transactions, preventing fraud and enhancing security. AI models evaluate risks associated with investments, loans, and insurance, aiding in comprehensive risk management.

Finally, AI significantly improves financial management. Automated financial analysis tools handle financial reporting, budgeting, and forecasting, provid-

ing accurate and timely financial insights. AI-driven algorithms analyze market data to develop and optimize investment strategies.

By integrating AI into various aspects of business operations, companies can achieve significant improvements in efficiency, customer satisfaction, and profitability, while also driving innovation and maintaining a competitive edge in the market.

Artificial intelligence provides significant benefits, including the ability to analyze large volumes of data, allowing you to make more accurate and informed decisions. It also helps optimize business processes, increasing efficiency and reducing costs. Personalizing the customer experience through tailored recommendations and offers improves customer interactions, while automating routine tasks frees employees from monotonous work, allowing them to focus on more important aspects of their work.

Digitalization and artificial intelligence are two key components of modern technologies that complement each other. Digitalization creates the infrastructure and data needed to make AI work, and AI, in turn, uses this data to create additional value and improve processes. Together they enable organizations to become more efficient, flexible and competitive.

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